

Report on Gender Equality

Bridging the Gender Gap

Jharkhand and West Bengal
2022-2023

By
PAIRVI

For
FAO ITPGRFA IV Cycle

Under the project

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

PAIRVI organized two days' workshop in Jharkhand and West Bengal states. Other states representative participated online and shared their views.

The main objective to determine and develop the parameters for gender equality in the project:

1. **Gender Balance:** Ensure that there is an equal representation of both men and women in the meeting.
2. **Speaking Time:** Monitor the speaking time of both men and women in the meeting to ensure that there is an equal distribution of speaking opportunities.
3. **Interrupting:** Watch out for instances of men interrupting women and vice versa. Encourage everyone to allow each other to finish their thoughts before speaking.
4. **Agenda Topics:** Ensure that the meeting agenda includes topics related to gender equality, diversity, and inclusion.
5. **Decision Making:** Ensure that both men and women have an equal say in decision making and that decisions are made based on merit and not gender.
6. **Action Items:** Ensure that action items are assigned equally to men and women and that they are based on individual skills and strengths.
7. **Feedback:** Provide a feedback mechanism for participants to give their opinions on how the meeting was conducted and how gender equality was maintained.
8. **Participation:** PAIRVI organized Survey in 2019-2020 in the project field and fact notice that women did not participate in government, KVK and other training programme related to agriculture extension. So, increase the participation of women in project meetings.

Gender Equality: Bridging the Gender Gap

15th March 2022
Murti, West Bengal

Background

The FAO and ITPGR funded piloting project on “Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population” is going on smoothly since 2019-2020. This innovative project is implemented by PAIRVI, New Delhi in five states including West Bengal. The aim of the project is to enhance the availability and on-farm conservation of resilient varieties of pulses and oil seeds for cultivation at rice fallow area of tribal belts. In West Bengal, this research project is being implemented in Matiali block of Jalpaiguri district among schedule caste and tribal households. The good number of women farmers is also included in this project for ensuring the inclusive development among the poor.

Considering this fact, the project is also emphasizing on gender and women development resulted in PAIRVI is conducting the Gender Equality Workshop in the respective project location of all five states.

Objectives

- Ensuring the gender equality is developed as an integral component of this project.
- Developing the internal structures and systems by ensuring equal participation of men and women like number of women participants in passbook distribution, trial farms, seed distribution, seed fair stall, FFS- farmers field school training, community seed bank management committee, varietal selection training etc.
- Bridging the gender gap resulted in conflicts reduced and adoption of new technologies are adopted.
- Discrimination between female and male farmers reduced and socio-economic development among the tribal population is taking place.

The Workshop

The gender equality workshop is organized by PAIRVI at Golden Head resort, Murthi, Jalpaiguri on 15th March 2022. There were 36 participants (male –13 and female -23) including 33 farmers from different project villages. The workshop is conducted in participatory way and facilitated by Mr. Vikas Arora, National Project Coordinator supported by state coordinator and field supervisor.

After the introduction, the workshop theme – Gender Equality towards bridging the gender gap is discussed in details. This is emphasized that it is a national and global issue. The inclusive development and its sustainability depend on gender equality. There should not be any discrimination between male and female. The example also given in the aspect of local context that male and female labours are working equally rather productive time of female wage labour is higher than male but female worker is getting Rs. 50/- to 70/- less than male. The truth and reality is accepted by all male and female participants in this workshop though we found most of the female participants are quite hesitant in-fronts of male.

Then Mr. Vikas Arora has discussed specific gender issues in the context project objectives and goals. He highlighted that equal participation of female and male farmers is very much required in opening the CSB- community seeds bank accounts so that at least 50% women can access seeds from CSB. The distribution of seeds or experimentation of the different trials plots to be also considered in following the gender balance principles. Mr. Arora also said that the project is also ensuring the implication of gender principles in conducting the different training and workshops like FFS- farmers field schools – at least 50% women need to participate in the different events organized by PAIRVI. He has requested to state coordinator to do the basic survey for distribution of seeds in bulk amount in the month of April 2022 for listing out

interested project participants with 50% female so that farmers can do land preparation and sowing in the month of May 2022.

The participants have appreciated the gender approaches of PAIRVI in the project location. The local project team including supervisor and volunteers are willing to follow the gender strategies very strictly.

Photos 1&2: Workshop is in progress

The participants are also requested to share their experiences of the project interventions for last 2 years in aspects of community seeds bank, gender and pulse/oilseeds cultivation. Both male and female farmers have openly shared their learning and experiences in the following manner / narratives-

1. Once again (after 20/25 years) we are involved in pulse and oil seeds cultivation. It is possible to revive the crops like black gram, arhar, lentil, mustard, tishi, sunflower etc. in this area.
2. Both male and female farmers (around 150) are well connected with the community seeds bank. We have mixed reaction about the yield.
3. We can ensure the better yield but two major threats – open grazing and wild animal to be protected from damaging the crops.
4. Mithun Oraon said “I have received 2 kg of black gram from seeds bank (CSB) and used 1.5 kg quality seeds after seeds treatment. I am happy that I used organic fertilizer and received 1.5 quintal quality black gram. I am very pleased and returned 6kg black gram to CSB for seed purpose in December 2021”
5. Esraful Islam: I received 2 kg black gram seeds from CSB and harvested it November 2021. The production was not so high but I am happy to receive 25 kg after harvesting. Now I know the reason behind low productivity. Next time I will do the same and expecting to achieve good yield.
6. Anita Roy said “I received 500gm Arhar seeds from CSB. Now I am having good growth plants and very happy to see them. In the month of Feb 2022 I harvested 10 kg arhar and

again I will harvest later from the same plants. I am very happy though threat of bird is a major problem. Good number of birds are coming together and eating the matured fruits.”

7. Basanti Lohar says “I received 25 to 30 kg black gram by using 2 kg seeds accessed from CSB.”
8. We including female are learning good experience and we are highly motivated. Whatever yield we are getting it gives us great satisfaction but our key learning is that yield can be enhanced by maintaining the right time of sowing. In this year of 2022 we will try to maintain it very strictly.
9. We are farmers but we are not getting enough training from govt / agriculture department. We need awareness and training from this project for ensuring better crops management.

Outcomes and way forward

The outcomes from this workshop are including the following-

- The participation of female farmers is more than male in this workshop. Both female and male farmers are actively participated as well as shared their learning and experience of the project.
- Both male and female farmers are accessing seeds from CSB and after harvesting returning more than double quantity of harvested crops for seed preservation.
- Some of the farmers are sowing the seeds after seeds treatment and cultivating it organically which is very encouraging. Need to promote it among all farmers including women. The project can create awareness on how to prepare the vermin compost and how to use organic cultivation.
- The farmers have realized from the project trials that timing of sowing of different crops is the key to ensure the higher productivity. The project team members need to prepare crop calendar more scientifically in discussion with the project farmers.
- The community seeds bank established in the project location is addressing the gender issues and both male and female farmers are covered under the CSB (enlisted 150 number of a/c holders so far). In this workshop the project decided to distribute another 100 accounts in next 12 months in balancing 50% women account holders.
- The major threat is open grazing and wild animals. The project needs to address this issue otherwise the momentum created by this project will be ruined and sustainability will be in question mark. The project has highlighted that we need to create human chain to protect the open grazing and to protect the wild animals. Same time modern technologies to be used. This is also suggested to communicate with forest department.
- To encourage and respect the project farmers, all farmers attended in the meeting received the participation certificates at the end of the workshop.
- The media covered the workshop and aired / published in the local channel and most circulated newspaper (Uttar Banga Sambad).

Photos 3&4: Participation Certificate to the participants and media press conference

Fig.: Certificate of Appreciation

Participants list

Sl.	Name	Institutions / Farmers
1.	Basanti Lohar	Farmer
2.	Anita Roy	Farmer
3.	Pompi Roy	Farmer
4.	Munni Kujur	Farmer
5.	Dipti Roy	Farmer
6.	Jayanti Roy	Farmer
7.	Rekha Roy	Farmer
8.	Rina Oraon	Farmer
9.	Nili Roy	Farmer
10.	Pramila Roy	Farmer
11.	Esaful Islam	Farmer
12.	Lakshmi Toppoo	Farmer
13.	Rina Roy	Farmer
14.	Sekender Rahaman	Farmer
15.	Suroti Roy	Farmer
16.	Mithun Oraon	Farmer

17.	Minoti Ekka	Farmer
18.	Kolin Roy	Farmer
19.	Tejbahadur Sonar	Farmer
20.	Chomme Oraon	Farmer
21.	Nobesh Roy	Farmer
22.	Alo Roy	Farmer
23.	Bhaleswari Roy	Farmer
24.	Anita Das	Farmer
25.	Dharani Roy	Farmer
26.	Pranesh Roy	Farmer
27.	Md. Mashud	Farmer
28.	Neha Roy	Farmer
29.	Masidul Islam	Farmer
30.	Mamoni Roy	Farmer
31.	Bamre Oraon	Farmer
32.	Rina Oraon	Farmer
33.	Bhaswati Roy	Farmer
34.	Mithun Roy	Supervisor
35.	Vikas Arora	Project Coordinator
36.	Dhananjay Ray	Coordinator

**Gender Equality:
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04 May 2022
Jharkhand

Introduction Session- 45 women participated in one day meeting. First of all, Subhash Dubey and Upender Kumar welcomed the participants by introducing himself from Bihar and Jharkhand and organization. PAIRVI Delhi's project coordinator Vikas Arora, while introducing himself, highlighted the objectives of the workshop and stated that there is a need to increase the area of cultivation of pulses and sesame with the tribal communities in the rice-growing areas of Bihar and Jharkhand. Since only one crop is grown in these areas by the farmers, they cultivate rice by taking advantage of the water from the lower land during the rainy season. However, they are unable to do anything with the upper land, which remains fallow. Therefore, in that fallow area, we make the tribal communities aware of cultivating pulses and sesame and increase the area of cultivation.

The session began with a cultural song performed by a tribal woman.

"Director of the PAIRVI Mr. Ajay Kumar Jha, addressed the participants present and Director of SBI told the participants that although they are all engaged in agriculture, it is necessary to learn about advanced farming techniques. He also advised the women present that they can earn extra money with a little effort during their free time by:

1. Making pickles
2. Making flower garlands. They can also cultivate flowers.
3. Rearing goats. We will provide information on how to rear goats and about their vaccination.
4. Learning sewing.

Therefore, I appeal to women not to waste their free time. By utilizing it, you can have a source of income. If there is a need for financial assistance for goat rearing, we will also provide a loan from the bank.

Dr. Ekta Rani Gurukul Coaching Director, addressing the gathering, said that both men and women work hard. For a person to live, they need three things: food, clothing, and shelter. A person progresses through their work. The society has developed a mindset that women are weak, but women are not weak. Today, women participate in every field. Education is essential for women to become empowered. If you are not educated, then make the next generation educated so that women can achieve equality in our society.

Educate your daughters so that they can become self-sufficient and live with dignity."

"It has been explained about lentils farming that it is very beneficial for health. It grows on sandy soil. Currently, we are experimenting with small things and considering working on women's self-employment."

The director of Mahila Kisan Adhikar Manch Mrs. Soma participated via online in meeting. The Mahila Kisan Adhikar Manch was established in 2016, which granted women farmers a status of their own. It has strong units in 21 states. The speaker further stated that 80% of agricultural work is carried out by women, but only 15% of farming is in the name of women. Women work just as hard as men, but they are not recognized in society. Due to the lack of rights for women in society, equality cannot be achieved. It is necessary to include women's names to give them their

rights. To ensure that women have the same rights as men, their names must be included in land ownership. By increasing women's leadership capabilities, they can obtain the right to equality.

Project coordinator Vikas Arora talked about the objective of FOA ITPGRFA project, he explained that how PAIRVI work with tribal farmers in Bihar and Jharkhand to utilize the fallow land for profitable crops such as pigeon pea and sesame by encouraging their cultivation. PAIRVI have established a community seed bank in each village of Bihar and Jharkhand, where farmers can obtain pigeon pea and sesame seeds and deposit their own seeds after harvesting. The seeds are distributed in the next season.

During the discussion on project development, the Jharkhand State Commissioner for Women Mrs. Basavi Kirvio stated that agriculture women has never been given importance in Jharkhand. More than one crop cannot be grown, and the value of land is very low. Production cannot meet the hard work put in. Jharkhand's tribal population relies heavily on forests and agriculture. Women gather firewood from the forest, which requires a lot of effort. In such a situation, Mandua (finger millet) roti is very beneficial for women to receive proper nutrition. Madua can also be ground into flour and used. Similarly, Mandua other many crops in Jharkhand has also been described as highly beneficial.
